
10. Catalogue data releases

GAIA WAS launched from Kourou, French Guiana, on 19 December 2013, and after a 6-month commissioning phase, started routine operations in July 2014.

Gaia continuously scans the sky following a carefully specified scanning ‘law’, providing a fairly uniform scanning of the celestial sphere, as well as a robust ‘separation’ of the astrometric parameters of each star.

There is no pre-defined observing programme. Instead, objects brighter than a specified threshold are detected as they enter the instrument’s fields of view, then followed as they cross the array of CCDs performing the astrometric, photometric, and radial velocity measurements. Typically, all stars brighter than about 21 mag are observed, including variable stars and moving objects. Just a handful are too bright to be observed.

Fundamental to the determination of absolute trigonometric parallaxes, Gaia has two widely separated fields of view, 106° apart. The angle between them is rigidly maintained, and the two fields of view are superimposed in the combined focal plane.

IN THE SIMPLEST case, a star’s location is characterised by its position on the sky at some reference epoch (e.g. the mid-point of the observations), given by two angular coordinates (RA and dec). Its space motion, projected on the plane of the sky, is characterised by its angular motion in both coordinates, usually expressed in milli-arcseconds (milli-arcsec or mas) per year.

A star’s finite distance results in an apparent change in its position as the Earth moves in its annual orbit around the Sun. From this parallax angle, typically measured in milli-arcsec (or mas) and denoted ϖ , its distance, in parsec, is determined as $d = 1/\varpi$.

Gaia can only measure radial velocities (and thus all 6 quantities specifying its position and motion in Euclidean space) for stars brighter than about 13 mag.

AS MORE measurements are accumulated over time, the accuracy on these various quantities improves. At the same time, observations over more than a year start to get a better measure of their proper motions, and

observations over more than 18–24 months start to get a much better separation between the effects of the star’s proper motion through space, and its parallax. For more complex binary or multiple stars, and especially in the case of orbital motion, more than 5 or 6 quantities are required to describe the star’s motion, and more observations are required to permit their estimation.

Successive catalogue releases comprise more observations, and as the temporal baseline increases, the accuracy of the astrometric parameters improves as a result of these two effects. Each successive catalogue supersedes the previous, so earlier data releases become redundant. In addition to orbital effects (due to binarity or planetary companions), more observations also give better handles on stellar variability, on the motion of solar system objects, and on systematic effects in the data (in particular the global parallax zero-point).

A summary of the three data releases to date are given in the table, and outlined below. My goal here is to summarise some key features useful in understanding the scientific use of the data. Many more details of each release are described under the given url’s.

GAIA DATA RELEASE 1 (DR1) is based on observations collected between 25 July 2014 and 16 September 2015, and was released on 14 September 2016.

It contains source identifier, positions (α , δ) and G magnitudes for sources with acceptable standard errors, the five-parameter astrometric solution (position, proper motion, and parallax) for stars in common between the Tycho 2 Catalogue (epoch around 1990) and Gaia (epoch around 2015), based on the Tycho–Gaia Astrometric Solution (TGAS).

DR1 was incomplete because of limitations in sky coverage, and data processing constraints. Many bright stars, $G < 7$, were missing, as were many fainter stars, sources close to bright objects, high proper motion stars, and stars in areas with very high surface densities (above some $400\,000\text{ deg}^{-2}$).

An A&A special issue in 2016 contained 16 papers describing the various aspects of the DR1 data release.

	Gaia DR1	Gaia DR2	Gaia EDR3	accuracy (indicative)
Observations:				
– time period	Jul 2014–Sep 2015	Jul 2014–May 2016	Jul 2014–May 2017	
– observations duration	14 months	22 months	34 months	
– reference epoch	J2015.0	J2015.5	J2016.0	
– catalogue release date	14 September 2016	25 April 2018	3 December 2020	
– url: www.cosmos.esa.int/web/gaia/dr1	gaia/dr1	gaia/dr2	gaia/earlydr3	see hyperlinks
Astrometry:				
– total number (3–21 mag)	1,142,679,769	1,692,919,135	1,811,709,771	0.01–1 mas
– 5-parameter solutions	2,057,050	1,331,909,727	585,416,709	
– 6-parameter solutions	2,057,050	–	882,328,109	
– 2-parameter solutions	1,140,622,719	361,009,408	343,964,953	
Photometry:				
– mean G magnitude	1,142,679,769	1,692,919,135	1,806,254,432	0.3–6 mmag
– mean G_{BP} photometry	–	1,381,964,755	1,542,033,472	1–100 mmag
– mean G_{RP} photometry	–	1,383,551,713	1,554,997,939	0.6–50 mmag
Radial velocities (4–13 mag)				
	–	7,224,631	7,209,831 (DR2)	0.2–3 km s ^{−1}
Other:				
– variable sources	3,194	550,737	as DR2	
– known asteroids with epoch data	–	14,099	as DR2	
– Gaia-CRF sources	2,191	556,869	as DR2	
– effective temperatures	–	161,497,595	as DR2	
– extinction and reddening	–	87,733,672	as DR2	
– radius and luminosity	–	76,956,778	as DR2	

GAIA DATA RELEASE 2 (DR2) was based on observations between 25 July 2014 and 23 May 2016, and was released on 25 April 2018.

As described under the relevant ESA Gaia [www](http://www.esa.int) pages (and where further details of various caveats are given), DR2 contains:

five-parameter astrometric solution (α , δ , μ_α , μ_δ , ϖ) for 1.3 billion sources in the range $G = 3 - 21$. Parallax uncertainties are up to 0.04 mas for $G < 15$, around 0.1 mas for $G = 17$ and around 0.7 mas at $G = 20$. Uncertainties in the proper motion components are up to 0.06 mas yr^{−1} ($G < 15$ mag), 0.2 mas yr^{−1} ($G = 17$ mag) and 1.2 mas yr^{−1} ($G = 20$ mag). DR2 parallaxes and proper motions are based only on Gaia data, and no longer depend on Tycho-2/TGAS.

two-parameter astrometric solution 361 million additional sources for which a two-parameter solution is available: the positions on the sky (α , δ) combined with the mean G magnitude. These have a positional uncertainty at $G = 20$ of about 2 mas (at J2015.5).

radial velocities Median radial velocities (i.e., the median value over the epochs) for 7.2 million stars with a mean $G = 4 - 13$ and $T_{\text{eff}} \sim 3550 - 6900$ K. This leads to a full six-parameter solution: positions and motions on the sky with parallaxes and radial velocities, all combined with mean G magnitudes. The overall radial velocity precision at the bright end is $\sim 200 - 300$ m s^{−1}, while at the faint end it is ~ 1.2 km s^{−1} for $T_{\text{eff}} = 4750$ K and ~ 2.5 km s^{−1} for $T_{\text{eff}} = 6500$ K.

G magnitudes for more than 1.69 billion sources, with precisions varying from around 1 mmag at $G < 13$ to ~ 20 mmag at $G = 20$. The photometric system for the G band in Gaia DR2 is different from the photometric system in Gaia DR1.

GBP and GRP magnitudes for more than 1.38 billion sources, with precisions varying from a few milli-mag at $G < 13$ to 200 mmag at $G = 20$. Passband definitions are given for G , G_{BP} and G_{RP} .

epoch astrometry for 14 099 known solar system objects based on more than 1.5 million CCD observations. 96% of the along-scan residuals are in the range -5 to 5 mas, and 52% are in the range -1 to 1 mas. The transit observations are part of Gaia DR2 and have also been delivered to the Minor Planet Center (MPC).

effective temperatures for 161 million sources brighter than 17 mag with $T_{\text{eff}} = 3000 - 10\,000$ K. For a subset of 87 million sources, the line-of-sight extinction A_G and reddening $E(BP- RP)$ are also given, and for a part of this subset (76 million sources) the luminosity and radius are also available.

classification for more than 550 000 variable sources consisting of Cepheids, RR Lyrae, Mira and Semi-Regular candidates as well as high-amplitude Delta Scu, BY Dra, and SX Phe candidates and short time scale phenomena.

A series of 25 papers in A&A Volume 216 (2018) describe the details of the Gaia DR2 data release.

GAIA DATA RELEASE 3 is split into two parts: the early release, Gaia Early Data Release 3 (Gaia EDR3), and the full Gaia Data Release 3 (Gaia DR3).

Gaia EDR3 was released on 3 December 2020, and the full Gaia Data Release 3 (Gaia DR3) is planned for the first half of 2022 [postscript: actually on 13 June 2022].

EDR3, as well as DR3, are based on observations between 25 July 2014 and 28 May 2017, i.e. a period of 34 months (compared with 14 months for DR1, and 22 months for DR2). The reference epoch for each release is given in the table.

AS DESCRIBED under the relevant ESA Gaia www pages (and where further details of various caveats are given), EDR3 contains:

five-parameter astrometric solution (α , δ , parallax, and proper motions) for 585 million sources, with a limiting magnitude of about $G \approx 21$ and a bright limit of about $G \approx 3$.

six-parameter astrometric solution a 6-parameter solution for a further 882 million sources includes a ‘pseudo-colour’, for sources lacking high-quality colour information.

two-parameter astrometric solution for around 344 million additional sources.

G magnitudes for around 1.806 billion sources.

G_{BP} and G_{RP} magnitudes for around 1.542 billion and 1.555 billion sources, respectively. The photometric system for the G , G_{BP} , and G_{RP} bands in Gaia EDR3 is different from the photometric system used in Gaia DR2 and Gaia DR1. Passband definitions are given for G , G_{BP} , and G_{RP} .

celestial reference frame sources for about 1.614 million celestial reference frame sources (Gaia-CRF3).

cross-matches between Gaia EDR3, and Gaia DR2, Hipparcos-2, Tycho-2 + TDSC merged, 2MASS PSC (merged with 2MASX), SDSS DR13, Pan-STARRS1 DR1, SkyMapper DR1, GSC 2.3, APASS DR9, RAVE DR5, allWISE, and URAT-1.

SOME FURTHER details of the typical accuracies, limitations, and caveats follow (see also some example plots on the following page):

- survey completeness: EDR3 is largely complete between $G = 12 - 17$. The source list for the release is incomplete at the bright end, and has an ill-defined faint magnitude limit, which depends on celestial position.

The combination of the ‘scanning law’ sky coverage, and some filtering on data, leads to some regions of the sky displaying source density fluctuations reflecting this scanning law pattern. In addition, small gaps exist in the source distribution, for example close to bright stars.

- coordinate system: positions and proper motions are referred to the ICRS (International Celestial Reference System), using TCB (barycentric coordinate time) as the fundamental time coordinate.

- astrometry: position uncertainties are 0.01–0.02 mas ($G < 15$), 0.05 mas ($G = 17$), 0.4 mas ($G = 20$), and 1.0 mas ($G = 21$). Parallax uncertainties are 0.02–0.03 mas ($G < 15$), 0.07 mas ($G = 17$), 0.5 mas ($G = 20$), and 1.3 mas ($G = 21$). Proper motion uncertainties are 0.02–0.03 mas yr⁻¹ ($G < 15$), 0.07 mas yr⁻¹ ($G = 17$), 0.5 mas yr⁻¹ ($G = 20$), and 1.4 mas yr⁻¹ ($G = 21$).

- parallax zero point: the parallax zero point deduced from extragalactic sources is about $-17 \mu\text{as}$. The uncertainties for the 6-parameter solutions are slightly larger than for 5-parameter solutions. Uncertainties for the 2-parameter solution (i.e. position only) are 1–3 mas.

- photometry: G -band standard errors are around 0.3 mmag ($G < 13$), 1 mmag ($G = 17$), and 6 mmag ($G = 20$). G_{BP} standard errors are around 0.9 mmag ($G < 13$), 12 mmag ($G = 17$), and 108 mmag ($G = 20$). G_{RP} standard errors are around 0.6 mmag ($G < 13$), 6 mmag ($G = 17$), and 52 mmag ($G = 20$).

- radial velocities: Gaia EDR3 (as Gaia DR2) contains median radial velocities for 7.21 million stars with $G \sim 4 - 13$ and T_{eff} in the range 3550–6900 K. The precision of the radial velocities is 200–300 m s⁻¹ at the bright end. At the faint end, accuracies are around 1.2 km s⁻¹ for $T_{\text{eff}} = 4750$ K and around 3.5 km s⁻¹ for $T_{\text{eff}} = 6500$ K.

- astrophysical parameters: some were published in DR2; no new updates were provided with Gaia EDR3.

- variable stars: some were classified in DR2; no new updates were provided with Gaia EDR3.

- solar system objects: information on the currently available asteroids was provided with Gaia DR2. Orbits will become available with the full Gaia DR3 release.

ASERIES OF papers in A&A (2021) describe the details of the Gaia EDR3 data release. These cover a summary of the contents and survey properties, as well as nine papers describing technical details of the data processing and calibration.

In addition, the data release was accompanied by four papers on selected science topics, viz. the Gaia catalogue of nearby stars, the structure and properties of the Magellanic Clouds, the Galactic anticentre, and the acceleration of the solar system from Gaia astrometry.

Some example statistical diagrams, given on the following page, are from gea.esac.esa.int/archive/documentation/GEDR3, where further details (and colour legends) can be found.

Further details of Gaia DR3 will be given separately when available [postscript: see essay #76, 13 June 2022].

Density counts for sources with a 5-parameter solution from EDR3 (Galactic coordinates). Densities range from around 100 (light blue) to some 10 000 (dark red) stars per square degree.

Median right ascension error for sources with a 5-parameter solution from EDR3 (Galactic coordinates). These range from below 50 micro-arcseconds (dark blue) to about 300 micro-arcseconds (dark red).

Median parallax error for sources with a 5-parameter solution from EDR3 (Galactic coordinates). These range from below 50 micro-arcseconds (dark blue) to about 300 micro-arcseconds (yellow).

Median of number of good astrometric observations for sources with a 5-parameter solution from EDR3 (Galactic coordinates). These range from about 200 (dark blue) to more than 1000 (red).